

ALGORITHM OF S-STAGE STOCHASTIC RUNGE-KUTTA METHOD FOR NUMERICAL SOLUTION OF STOCHASTIC DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

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Abstract

Runge-Kutta method is an iterative method for numerical solution of differential equations. The purpose this paper to investigate an algorithm of stochastic Runge-Kutta method for numerical solution of stochastic differential equations (SDEs). Because, most SDEs do not have analytical solution. Hence, numerical solution is required to estimate the numerical solution of SDEs. In addition, we applied this algorithm for numerical solution of Logistic Stochastic Differential Equation for cell concentration.

Keywords: Wiener Process, Stochastic Differential Equation, S-Stage Stochastic Runge-Kutta method.

1. Introduction

Ordinary differential equations (ODEs) are extensively used to model the natural science phenomena in the last centuries. Meanwhile, the processes which are modelled via ODEs are suffering from random fluctuations and these random fluctuations were neglected (Ayoubi et al., 2015). It means the ODEs models are not adequate models to model the phenomena. Therefore, this problem has been solved via SDEs and these models have been used to model natural science namely, Physics (Sobczyk, 2013), Agriculture (Krouwel et al., 1983), Finance (Evans, 2012; Shreve, 2004), Health (Elowitz, 2002) and for Mobile Service (Olama et al., 2009) etc. Most of SDEs do not have explicit solution but these equations can be solved numerically, to approximate the solution of them (Ayoubi, 2015). Therefore, current paper investigates an algorithm of 2-stage and 4-stage SRK for numerical solution of SDEs.

The German mathematician's Carl David Tolme Runge (1856-1927) and Martin Wilhelm Kutta (1867-1944) which are known as Runge-Kutta developed the Euler method to ODEs,

$$y'(t) = f(y(t)), y(t_0) = y_0 \wedge y \in \check{Y}^n \quad (1)$$

and allowed multiple function to evaluate single numerical step (Burrage et al., 1994). It was Kutta (1901) who extended this approach and characterized the set of Runge-Kutta with 4th-stage (Burrage et al., 1994). Now this method is famous in the name of 4-stage Runge-Kutta method:

$$\begin{aligned} Y_1 &= y_0 \\ Y_2 &= y_n + \frac{1}{2} hf(Y_1) \\ Y_3 &= y_n + \frac{1}{2} hf(Y_2) \\ Y_4 &= y_n + \frac{1}{2} hf(Y_3) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

This is the basic idea for both explicit and implicit approach which led to approximate the numerical solution. Primary numerical method for SDEs is Euler-Maruyama that introduced by Maruyama (1950). This approach was extended based on stochastic Taylor

truncation. Euler-Maruyama has diminutive convergence which is 0.5 order, for numerical approximation of SDEs. In addition, for numerical approximation there are two more numerical methods to approximate the solution of SDEs such as, Milstein scheme and Runge-Kutta method, respectively. Milstein scheme is introduced by Milstein (1994) with 1.0 order convergence and this scheme explained by Glasserman (2003) for general process. The other numerical method which is more accurate than Euler-Maruyama and Milstein scheme is stochastic Runge-Kutta (SRK) method (Norhayati et al., 2010). Thus, this research provides algorithm for 2-stage and 4-stage SRK method for numerical approximation of SDEs however the s-stage explicit method is iterative numerical method to approximate the numerical solution of SDE and it was purposed by Rumellin (1982) which was based on Brownian motion.

The classical Brownian Motion term was introduced by Scottish botanist Robert Brown in (1827). He described this motion based on random movements of pollen grains in liquid or gas. He posed this problem in case of mathematics which describes the movements of pollen grains in liquid but he did not solve the problem himself (Mishura et al., 2008). The first time Brownian motion has been used by Bachelier (1900) to model stock prices in Paris Bourse and followed by German physicist Albert Einstein (1906) to measure the number of molecules in a mole of gas (Chung et al., 2006; Evans, 2012, p35). Norbert Wiener (1923) introduced full mathematical theory of Brownian motion which exists as a rigorously defined mathematical objective to recognize his contribution. Brownian motion is a simple continuous stochastic process which is extensively used to model phenomena in various fields such as industry, dynamic process, fermentation process, physics and finance (Mazo, 2002). In addition, for modeling random variation which is evolves over time. For example, to model the behavior of random movements in a molecule of gas and fluctuations in an asset's price. Thus, random variable is defined as Wiener process which is illustrated with details in definition (1) (Karatzas et al., 2012).

This paper is organized in seven sections which are; Introduction, Wiener Process, Stochastic Defereential Equation, SRK Method for SDE, Algorithm of S-

stage SRK for SDEs, Conclusion, Acknowledgment and References. Prior approaching main concepts, we deliberate on some of the basic senses which will assist the investigation process to reach the main subject as presented below;

Definition (1): Wiener Process (Oksendal, 1995)

Stochastic process, $W(t)$, $0 \leq t < T$, in a continuous time known as Wiener process and it is following the bellow properties:

(i) $W(t_0) = 0, P(W(t)) = 1.$

(ii) The increment of $W(t)$ are independent, for any finite time $0 \leq t_1 < t_2 < t_3 < \dots < T$ the random variable

$W(t_2) - W(t_1), W(t_3) - W(t_2), W(t_4) - W(t_3), \dots, W(t_n) - W(t_{n-1})$

are independent.

(iii) For any $0 \leq s < t < T$,

$W(t) - W(s)$ has Gaussian distribution with mean zero and variance $t - s$.

(iv) At time t , $W(t, \omega)$ is continuous

function for all $\omega \in \Omega$.

By taking into account, the above definition of Wiener process, it has sample paths which are continuous but not differentiable in any point. On the other hand, a glance at simulated Brownian paths convinces us that its sample paths are extremely irregular. The property of independent increments is the main reason of this irregularity. It is obvious that

$$\lim_{\Delta \rightarrow 0} \frac{(W_{t_0+\Delta} - W_{t_0})}{\Delta}$$

does not exist (Žitković, 2010). Therefore, Wiener process is non-differentiable. Wiener motion also does not have bounded variation on a finite time $[0, T]$, that

$$\sup \sum |W_{t_i}(\omega) - W_{t_{i-1}}(\omega)| = \infty$$

where

$$P := \{0 = t_0 < t < t_2 < t_3 < \dots < t_n = T\}$$

Figure (1): Wiener process in two dimension for time, $t=100$.

Figure (1) shows the sample path of Wiener process at time t .

2. STOCHASTIC DIFFERENTIAL EQUATION

Einstein's and Smoluchowski were the earliest men who worked on SDEs to illustrate the Brownian motion. Later Bachelier (1900) on his thesis described theory of speculation in Brownian motion and this work was followed by Langevin. Meanwhile, Ito and Stratonovich worked on mathematical theory of SDEs to become more and more drastic. This paper provides a numerical algorithm to approximate numerical solution of SDEs either. Now, the most important question that what is stochastic differential equation (SDE) and why we study SDE?

SDE is defined as random fluctuation with ordinary differential equation (ODE) (Ayoubi, 2015). All processes are producing equipment via mathematical models, these processes are suffering from random fluctuation. This random fluctuation cannot be accounted via ODE because of random movements, therefore it is required to model via SDE. To interpret more the SDE model. Let us consider an example from mathematics, suppose we have the quantity $y(t)$, $t \geq 0$ which indicates the cell concentration in

a process at time t . By taking into account, the variation $\Delta y = y(t + \Delta t) - y(t)$ of process in small time interval $[t, t + \Delta t)$. This variations in a process are defined as the ratio $\frac{\Delta y}{y}$.

$$\frac{\Delta y}{y}$$

$\frac{\Delta y}{y} = \text{Deterministic Contribution} + \text{Stochastic Contribution}$

$$\frac{\Delta y}{y} = \mu \Delta t + \sigma \Delta W$$

The deterministic section is corresponding to the interest rate of non-risky activities and hence compatible to time with some constant rate μ ,

$$\mu \Delta t = \text{Deterministic Contribution}$$

The stochastic section is relating to the random fluctuation (noise) in the process. This variation can be clarified by $\Delta y = y(t + \Delta t) - y(t)$. This instability σ , is destroying the commensurate of process. Hence,

$$\sigma \Delta W = \text{Stochastic Contribution}$$

where, σ also can be a function of t or y and $\Delta y \square N(0,1)$ is hypothesis which illustrates the

Gaussian behavior of noise. Moreover, assumed to be independent so, the general form of the first order SDE can be formulated as equation (3)

$$dy(t) = f(t, y(t))dt + g(t, y(t))dW(t) \quad (3)$$

where $W(t)$ illustrates a d -dimensional Wiener process, $g(t, y(t))$ indicates $m \times d$ -

matrix-valued function, $f(t, y(t))$ is related to m -vector valued function and $y(t)$ is m -vector stochastic process. In integration form, equation (3) is;

$$y(t) = y(t_0) + \int_0^t f(s, y(s))ds + \int_0^t g(s, y(s))dW(s) \quad (4)$$

The first right side of integral (4) is easy to calculate because, it is Riemann-Stieltjes integral but the second hand side is a little difficult to calculate. It is respect to stochastic process (Wiener Process), which interpreted as stochastic integral. For every $\omega \in \Omega$, the

sample path $W(t, \omega)$ is nowhere differentiable and does not have bounded variation. Stochastic integral is described into two forms which are can be either Stratonovich or Itô integrals. This analysis is depending on assessment of valued integrand. The Riemann sums approximation is

$$R := \sum_{i=1}^k g(r_i, y(r_i))(W(t_i) - W(t_{i-1})), \quad r_i \in [t_{i-1}, t_i] \quad (5)$$

For $t_{i-1} \leq r_i \leq t_i$, the sum is given by equation (5) converges in mean-square to different values of integral. Therefore, it is time to

show how the integration of $\int_a^b W(t)dW(t)$ is estimated. Let consider the following expression

$$\varphi_n^v = vW(t_k^{(n)}) + (1-v)W(t_{k-1}^{(n)}), \quad t_{k-1}^{(n)} \leq t \leq t_k^{(n)} \quad (6)$$

for any fixed $v \in [0, 1]$. The integral form of φ_n^v in interval $a \leq t \leq b$, is respected to the Wiener process and estimated via

$$\int_a^b \varphi_n^v(t)dW(t) = \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_n^v(t_{k-1}^{(n)})(W(t_k^{(n)}) - W(t_{k-1}^{(n)})) \quad (7)$$

By substituting (6) into (7), the following Riemann estimation is achieved

$$v \sum_{k=1}^n (W(t_k^{(n)}) - W(t_{k-1}^{(n)})) + (1-v) \sum_{k=1}^n W(t_{k-1}^{(n)})(W(t_k^{(n)}) - W(t_{k-1}^{(n)})) \quad (8)$$

By arranging the equation (8) algebraically yield;

$$\sum_{k=1}^n W(t_{k-1}^{(n)})(W(t_k^{(n)}) - W(t_{k-1}^{(n)})) = \frac{1}{2} W(t_k^{(n)})^2 - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n (W(t_k^{(n)}) - W(t_{k-1}^{(n)}))^2 \quad (9)$$

and

$$\sum_{k=1}^n W(t_k^{(n)})(W(t_k^{(n)}) - W(t_{k-1}^{(n)})) = \frac{1}{2} W(t_k^{(n)})^2 - \frac{1}{2} W(t_0^{(n)})^2 - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n (W(t_k^{(n)}) - W(t_{k-1}^{(n)}))^2$$

for each $a = t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_n = b$. Therefore, the estimation of (8) is

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_n^v(t_{k-1}^{(n)})(W(t_k^{(n)}) - W(t_{k-1}^{(n)})) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} W(t_k^{(n)})^2 - \frac{1}{2} W(t_0^{(n)})^2 + \frac{1}{2} (2v-1) \sum_{k=1}^n (W(t_k^{(n)}) - W(t_{k-1}^{(n)}))^2 \end{aligned}$$

For each k , the mean-square limit of

$$E(W(t_k^{(n)}) - W(t_{k-1}^{(n)}))^2 = t_k - t_{k-1} \quad (10)$$

The interval $[a, b]$ is divided into n subintervals, $\Delta = \frac{b-a}{n}$. To conclude, the mean square limit of sum squares in (8) is $n\Delta = b-a$ and the mean square of (7) is:

$$\int_a^b W(t) dW(t) = \frac{1}{2} (W^2(b) - W^2(a)) + \left(v - \frac{1}{2} \right) (b - a) \tag{11}$$

if $\Delta \rightarrow 0$. Different results will be achieved for diverse $0 \leq v \leq 1$. For the left side of interval, $v = 0$ or $\tau_i = t_{i-1}$ is considered. Therefore, the integral will be raised based on Itô chain rules. Meanwhile, if the $v = \frac{1}{2}$ or $\tau_i = \frac{t_i + t_{i-1}}{2}$, which are midpoint in interval $[a, b]$ thus, the results will be raised based on Stratonovich integral. Stratonovich integral is based on Riemann-Stiltjes integral rules. This integral is simpler than the Itô integral. Euler- Maruyama and Milstein scheme are developed based on Itô and Stratonovich calculus for numerical solution of SDEs. However, SRK4 for SDEs is relied on the Stratonovich calculus but Itô calculus is not consistent with SRK4 method Ayoubi (2015).

Most of SDEs do not have explicit solution therefore it is numerical solution which provide a method to approximate the solution of SDEs. The following section considers explicit stochastic 2-stage and 4-stage Runge-Kutta method for numerical solution of SDEs.

3. NUMERICAL SOLUTION

Numerical solution of SDEs is very young concept in mathematics field. There are three methods for numerical approximation of SDEs such as Euler-Maruyama method, Milstein scheme and Runge-Kutta method. Euler-Maruyama is the simplest numerical method for SDE which is proposed by Maruyam (1950). This approach was extended based on stochastic Taylor truncation and Milstein scheme was introduced by Milstein (1994) with 1.0 order convergence. The other numerical method which is much more accurate than Euler-Maruyama and Milstein scheme is stochastic Runge-Kutta (SRK) method. This method was introduced by Rumellin (1982). SRK was developed based on the increment of Wiener process,

$$J_1(t) = \int_{t_n}^{t_{n+1}} dW(t) .$$

The general form of SRK for numerical approximation SDEs is:

$$Y_i = Y_n + \Delta \sum_{i=1}^s a_{ij} f(Y_j^n) + J_1 \sum_{i=1}^s b_{ij} g(Y_j), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, s \tag{12}$$

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + \Delta \sum_{i=1}^s \alpha_i f(Y_i^n) + J_1 \sum_{i=1}^s \gamma_i g(Y_j)$$

where, $\mathbf{A} = (a_{ij})_{s \times s}$ and $\mathbf{B} = (b_{ij})_{s \times s}$ are matrices of real elements, $\boldsymbol{\alpha}^T = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_s)$ and $\boldsymbol{\gamma}^T = (\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_s)$ are row vectors. Burrage et al., (1996) introduced new formulation for SRK which is depended on stochastic components of J_1 and $\frac{J_{10}}{\Delta}$. This stochastic components comes from J_1 integral. Because the SRK (12) is not able to present convergence order 1.0. Therefore, the SRK formulation is

$$Y_i^n = Y_n + \sum_{j=1}^s Z_{ij}^{(0)} f(Y_j) + \sum_{j=1}^s Z_{ij}^{(1)} g(Y_j), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, s \tag{13}$$

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + \sum_{i=1}^s z_i^{(0)} f(Y_i) + J_1 \sum_{i=1}^s z_i^{(1)} g(Y_i)$$

where $Z_{ij}^{(0)}, Z_{ij}^{(1)}, z_i^{(0)}$ and $z_i^{(1)}$ can be written

$$Z_{ij}^{(0)} = \Delta a_{ij}, \quad i, j = 1, \dots, s \tag{14}$$

$$Z_{ij}^{(1)} = \sum_{l=1}^q b_{ij}^{(l)} \theta_l, \quad i, j = 1, \dots, s \tag{15}$$

$$z_i^{(0)} = \Delta \alpha_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, s \tag{16}$$

$$z_i^{(1)} = \sum_{l=1}^q \gamma_i^{(l)} \theta_l, \quad i = 1, \dots, s \tag{17}$$

The SRK will have strong order 1.0 and 1.5, when $q = 2$, then $\theta_1 = J_1$ and $\theta_2 = \frac{J_{10}}{\Delta}$,

Where

$$J_{10} = \int_{t_n}^{t_{n+1}} \int_{t_n}^t dW(s)dt$$

and it is approximated via

$$\frac{J_{10}}{\Delta} = \frac{\sqrt{\Delta}}{2} \left(N_1 + \frac{N_2}{\sqrt{3}} \right)$$

where N_1 and N_2 are presenting normal distribution with, $\mu = 0$ and $\sigma^2 = 1$. Thus, S -stage SRK is

$$\begin{aligned} Y_i &= y_n + \Delta \sum_{j=1}^s a_{ij}^{(0)} f(Y_j) + \sum_{j=1}^s \left(b_{ij}^{(1)} J_1 + b_{ij}^{(2)} \frac{J_{10}}{\Delta} \right) g(Y_j), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, s \\ y_{n+1} &= y_n + \Delta \sum_{i=1}^s \alpha_i^{(0)} f(Y_i) + \sum_{i=1}^s \left(\gamma_i^{(1)} J_1 + \gamma_i^{(2)} \frac{J_{10}}{\Delta} \right) g(Y_i) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Burrage et al., (1996) proposed 4-stage stochastic Runge-Kutta method (SRK4) based on (18). This method has strong order 1.5. The SRK4 approach can be written as

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & & & \\ \frac{1}{2} & 0 & & \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{B}^{(1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & & & & \\ -0.7242916356 & 0 & & & \\ 0.42373534060 & -0.1994437050 & 0 & & \\ -1.5784755060 & 0.84010034000 & 1.738375163 & 0 & \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

$$\mathbf{B}^{(2)} = \begin{bmatrix} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 2.7002000410 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \\ 1.7572616490 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \\ -2.918524118 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}^T = \left[\frac{1}{6} \quad \frac{1}{3} \quad \frac{1}{3} \quad \frac{1}{6} \right]$$

$$\boldsymbol{\gamma}^{(1)T} = [-0.7800788474 \quad 0.07363768240 \quad 1.4865200130 \quad 0.21992115240]$$

$$\boldsymbol{\gamma}^{(2)T} = [1.69395084400 \quad 1.63610788200 \quad -3.024009558 \quad -0.3060491602]$$

4-stage SRK has better performance 2-stage SRK in approximating the solutions of SDE (Norhayati et al., 2010). This research presents an algorithm for 4-stage SRK method. This method is presented in bellow section.

4. ALGORITHM OF 2-STAGE AND 4-STAGE STOCHASTIC RUNGE-KUTTA METHOD

Algorithm illustrates serval steps to realize an errand but in mathematics algorithm indicates to the serval steps to find an explicit solution either numerical or analytical. Almost all algorithms which are using for numerical approximation of SDEs are taken from of

ODEs. These algorithms work very poor and having very poor numerical convergence. However, there are some a few works on algorithm of SDEs for numerical solution namely, (Higham, 2001) works on Euler-Maruyama method and Milstein scheme and Lourakis (2005) describes Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) algorithm for numerical approximation but this paper illustrates an algorithm of 2-stge and 4-stage stochastic Runge-Kutta method for numerical solution of SDEs and it is presented in bellow;

1. Inpute parametr.
2. Set end steps.

3. Do drift function, $f(t, y(t))$.
4. Do diffusion functions, $g(t, y(t))$.
5. Perform random number generator.
6. Compute the stages Y_1, Y_2, Y_3 and Y_4 .
7. Perform an explicit 2-stage and 4-stage SRK.

In mathematics, algorithm is a collection of steps which provides a clear approach to accumulate the solution of equations. The solution can be either numerical or analytical solution. Algorithm is the key of decision in a process and guide us to go the next step or not to go further. In addition, algorithm aids us to reach on

achievement very fast and analyze the solution more accurate and a clear way. Moreover, it provides clear steps to analysis the strong and weak points of the solution and controlling the analysis. This algorithm which proposed in current research, helps us to approximate the numerical solution of SDEs step by step via 2-stage and 4-stage SRK. Especially when we are transferring the parameters, initial values, drift function, diffusion function and stages into C language. The algorithm is better described in bellow flowchart.

Figure¹¹ (3): Flowchart on numerical simulation of SDE.

However, recently number of researchers who are analyzing the numerical methods of SDEs rapidly increase. It can be seen (Kloeden, et al., 1992; Milstein, 1994; Burrage, et al., 1996; Higham, 2001; Rosli, et al., 2013; Xiao, et al., 2016).

To make obvious our assert, let us consider an example which is stochastic logistic model for cell concentration. In this example we applied this algorithm for 2-stage and 4-stage SRK for numerical solution (20) and showed how this algorithm is working,

¹¹ This algorithm is proposed in current research.

$$x(t) = x_0 + \int_0^T \mu_{\max} \left(1 - \frac{x(t)}{x_{\max}} \right) x(t) dt + \int_0^T \sigma x^2(t) dW(t) \quad (20)$$

where, x_0 indicates to the initial cell size at time $t = 0$, x_{\max} denotes the maximum cell concentration, μ_{\max} shows to the maximum specific growth rate of microbial growth, σ illustrates noise and diffusion coefficient, T is terminal time and $w(t)$ Wiener process. Equation (20) is one of the SDEs which has not analytical solution. We used 4-stage SRK method to approximate the numerical solution that is presenting in bellow;

$$\begin{aligned} Y_1 &= y_n \\ Y_2 &= y_n + \frac{1}{2} \Delta f(Y_1) + \left((-0.72429163) J_1 + (2.7700200410) \frac{J_{10}}{\Delta} \right) g(Y_1) \\ Y_3 &= y_n + \Delta \frac{1}{2} f(Y_2) + \left((0.42373534) J_1 + (1.75261649) \frac{J_{10}}{\Delta} \right) g(Y_1) + (-0.19944370) J_1 g(Y_2) \\ Y_4 &= y_n + \Delta f(Y_3) + \left((-1.5784755) J_1 + (-2.9918524118) \frac{J_{10}}{\Delta} \right) g(Y_1) + (0.84010043) J_1 g(Y_2) \\ &\quad + (1.73837510) J_1 g(Y_3) \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} y_{n+1} &= y_n + \Delta \left(\frac{1}{6} f(Y_1) + \frac{1}{3} f(Y_2) + \frac{1}{3} f(Y_2) + \frac{1}{6} f(Y_4) \right) + \left((-0.78007) J_1 + (1.69395) \frac{J_{10}}{\Delta} \right) g(Y_1) \\ &\quad + \left((0.073637) J_1 + (1.63610) \frac{J_{10}}{\Delta} \right) g(Y_2) + \left((1,4865) J_1 + (-3.02400) \frac{J_{10}}{\Delta} \right) g(Y_3) \\ &\quad + \left((0.21992) J_1 + (-0.306049) \frac{J_{10}}{\Delta} \right) g(Y_4) \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

By taking into account numerical method of (19) to a stochastic model (20) we get

$$\begin{aligned} Y_1 &= y_n \\ Y_2 &= y_n + \frac{1}{2} \Delta \left(\mu_{\max} \left(1 - \frac{Y_1}{x_{\max}} \right) Y_1 \right) + \left(-0.7242916356 J_1 + 2.7700200410 \frac{J_{10}}{\Delta} \right) \sigma Y_1^2 \\ Y_3 &= y_n + \frac{1}{2} \Delta \left(\mu_{\max} \left(1 - \frac{Y_2}{x_{\max}} \right) Y_2 \right) + \left(0.42373534060 J_1 + 1.7572616490 \frac{J_{10}}{\Delta} \right) \sigma Y_1^2 \\ &\quad + (-0.1994437050) J_1 \sigma Y_2^2 \\ Y_4 &= y_n + \Delta \left(\mu_{\max} \left(1 - \frac{Y_3}{x_{\max}} \right) Y_3 \right) + \left(-1.5784755060 J_1 + (-2.918524118) \frac{J_{10}}{\Delta} \right) \sigma Y_1^2 \\ &\quad + 0.84010034000 J_1 \sigma Y_2^2 + 1.738375163 J_1 \sigma Y_3^2 \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 y_{n+1} = y_n + \Delta & \left[\frac{1}{6} \left(\mu_{\max} \left(1 - \frac{Y_1}{x_{\max}} \right) Y_1 \right) + \frac{1}{3} \left(\mu_{\max} \left(1 - \frac{Y_2}{x_{\max}} \right) Y_2 \right) \right. \\
 & \left. + \frac{1}{3} \left(\mu_{\max} \left(1 - \frac{Y_3}{x_{\max}} \right) Y_3 \right) + \frac{1}{6} \left(\mu_{\max} \left(1 - \frac{Y_4}{x_{\max}} \right) Y_4 \right) \right] \\
 & + \left(-0.7800788474J_1 + 1.69395084400 \frac{J_{10}}{\Delta} \right) \sigma Y_1^2 \\
 & + \left(0.07363768240J_1 + 1.63610788200 \frac{J_{10}}{\Delta} \right) \sigma Y_2^2 \\
 & + \left(1.4865200130J_1 + (-3.024009558) \frac{J_{10}}{\Delta} \right) \sigma Y_3^2 \\
 & + \left(0.21992115240J_1 + (-0.3060491602) \frac{J_{10}}{\Delta} \right) \sigma Y_4^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

This algorithm has been used by (Ayoubi, 2019; Ayoubi, & Khirzada, 2020 and Ayoubi, T., & Bao, 2020). Next section illustrates the simulated result of 2-stage and 4-stage SRK for cell concentration.

5. SIMULATED RESULT OF 2-STAGE AND 4-STAGE SRK FOR CELL CONCENTRATION

This section reflects the quality approximation of mathematical models to explain the behavior of the cell growth. The maximum cell concentration, x_{\max} and initial values of $x(t_0)$ are taken from the experimental data which has been collected by Madihah (2002). It is viewed in Table (1).

Table (1):

Initial values and maximum cell concentration for (yeast extract) YE.

Initial value	YE
$x(t_0)$	0.0031
x_{\max}	3.5250

Table (2) illustrates the estimated values of μ_{\max} and σ for YE1. The estimated values for SDE are taken from Bazli (2010) except for σ . Based on Tables (1) and (2) the bellow figures are plotted in Matlab program by using stochastic logistic equation (20) with data for YE.

Table(2):

Estimated values of μ_{\max} , σ and r for YE.

Mathematical model	Estimated values	YE
SDE	μ_{\max}	0.4500
	σ	0.0026

Now we can apply this algorithm for numerical solution of SDEs via 4-stage stochastic Runge-Kutta method.

Figure (4): 2-stage SRK of logistic stochastic equation versus experimental data.

Figure (5): 4-stage SRK of logistic stochastic equation versus experimental data.

Table (3):

Mean square error for 4-Stage SRK and 2-Stage SRK		
Numerical Methods	4-Stage SRK	2-Stage SRK
Mean Square Error	2.53	2.81

It is obvious from Table (3), the 4-stage SRK has closest result which is compared to the experimental data than 2-stage SRK. Because the 2-stage SRK is estimating only the stochastic integral J_1 and overlook the stochastic integrals $\frac{J_{10}}{\Delta}$, therefore the 2-stage presents poor result than 4-stage SRK method.

6. CONCLUSION

The description of various phenomena in natural science leads to solve a differential equations. Hence, the answers of these types of equations is important, since the analytical solutions of these equations have a specific complexity type, and sometimes analytical solutions of these equations are not available. So, numerical solution is required. Therefore, in this research we have successfully constructed the algorithm for 2-stage and 4-stage SRK method to approximate the numerical solution of SDEs. In addition, we applied this algorithm in particular case which is logistic stochastic equations for cell concertation to proof our assert and how this algorithm is working for both which is constructed in

this research. Moreover, we calculate mean square error to 2-stage SRK and 4-stage SRK to show the difference between both methods.

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